

The Effect of Content Marketing and Fear of Missing Out to Post-Purchase Regret Mediated by Impulsive Buying

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine and discuss the influence of Content Marketing and Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) on Post-purchase regret through Impulsive Buying as a Mediating Variable. The type of research used is quantitative research. The sample used was 100 respondents who were buyers and users of Somethinc products and were active members of the Twitter community (X) "Oh My Beauty Bank". The sampling technique used was non-probability sampling with purposive sampling. The data collection method was with Google Form. Data analysis used SmartPLS. The results of this study concluded that Content Marketing had a significant effect on Impulsive Buying, FoMO had a significant effect on Impulsive Buying, Content Marketing had a significant effect on Post-purchase Regret, and FoMO had a significant effect on Post-purchase Regret.

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KEYWORDS:

Content Marketing, Fear of Missing Out, Impulsive Buying, Post-purchase Regret.

INTRODUCTION

Advances in digital technology and increased internet access have brought about significant transformations in consumer behavior, particularly in the context of digital marketing. One approach increasingly employed by businesses to attract consumer interest is content marketing. This strategy refers to a marketing method that strategically focuses on creating and distributing useful, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain audience attention (Pulizzi, 2012). In practice, content marketing is not only used to build brand awareness but also to influence purchasing decisions, including encouraging impulse buying behavior.

At the same time, the phenomenon of FoMO is also gaining increasing attention in today's digital consumer behavior. FoMO represents the anxiety experienced by individuals due to the fear of missing out on experiences enjoyed by others, which is often exacerbated by exposure to social media content (Przybylski et al., 2013). Several studies have shown that FoMO can trigger spontaneous purchasing decisions, when consumers are compelled to make immediate purchases to avoid feeling left out (Hodkinson, 2019).

One impact of impulsive buying triggered by content marketing and FoMO is post-purchase regret, the emergence of regret after making a purchase. This condition is a serious concern in managing customer satisfaction, as it has the potential to reduce loyalty and decrease the likelihood of repeat purchases (Tsiros & Mittal, 2000). Therefore, understanding impulsive buying behavior is not only important as part of consumer dynamics but can also serve as a mediating variable, bridging the influence of content marketing and FoMO on post-purchase regret.

However, most previous research has been limited to the influence of content marketing on purchasing decisions or consumer engagement with brands in general (Hollebeek & Macky, 2019), as well as the relationship between FoMO and social media usage (Przybylski et al., 2013). Research examining the relationship between content marketing and FoMO on post-purchase regret, while considering impulsive buying as an intermediary variable, is still rare. This indicates a research gap that is important to fill, especially in the context of digital consumers in Indonesia who are highly active users of social media and online shopping platforms.

The novelty of this study lies in the development of a theoretical model that simultaneously integrates the influence of content marketing and FoMO on post-purchase regret through impulsive buying as a mediator. Furthermore, this research also contributes to the literature in digital marketing by adding a deeper perspective on consumer psychology to understand the dynamics of unplanned purchases and the emotional impact of post-purchase. It is hoped that the results of this study can provide practical input for marketers in developing more ethical communication strategies oriented towards long-term customer satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Content Marketing

Content marketing is a marketing strategy focused on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, engaging, and consistent content to attract and retain audience attention. Content can be in the form of text, images, video, audio, or other digital forms, and is typically distributed through websites or social media (Pulizzi, 2014; Kotler & Keller, 2016; Frost & Judy, 2016). The primary goal of content marketing is to communicate with consumers indirectly but effectively, to build relationships, influence purchasing decisions, and achieve a company's business goals (Ramos, 2013; Vinerean, 2017). To create effective content, several factors need to be considered (Kumalasanti, 2022), namely attractive and aesthetic visual design, alignment with current events, a pleasant and easy-to-understand reading experience, appropriate and consistent publication timing, and a tone that suits the characteristics of the target audience. The quality of content marketing can be measured through six key indicators (Milhinhos, 2015): relevance of information to consumer needs, accuracy of fact-based content, value to the audience, ease of understanding, ease of discovery on the right channels, and consistency in regular content delivery. By paying attention to these aspects, content marketing can be a highly strategic tool in building long-term relationships between brands and consumers.

Fear of Missing Out

FoMO is a psychological condition in which individuals feel anxious and afraid of being left out of social experiences that are considered enjoyable or valuable by others, especially those seen through social media or the internet (Przybylski et al., 2013). The desire to stay connected and know what others are doing is a key characteristic of this phenomenon. FOMO can cause stress, anxiety, and dissatisfaction with personal life due to social comparisons reinforced by digital media. According to Przybylski et al. (2013), FOMO arises from unmet psychological needs for relatedness and psychological needs related to competence and autonomy. Indicators of FoMO, according to Reagle (2015), include comparison with friends, being left out, missed experiences, and compulsion.

Impulsive Buying

Impulsive buying is spontaneous purchasing behavior carried out without prior planning, triggered by a momentary emotional urge upon seeing a product (Stern, 1962; Wirawan, 2016; Utami, 2016). Consumers tend to buy products suddenly due to environmental stimuli, such as promotions or product displays, without considering the need or consequences (Rook & Fisher, 1995). In some cases, impulsive buying is also related to psychological conditions such as stress or the desire to improve mood (Samuel, 2005). According to Ermy (2018), several factors influence impulsive buying, namely shopping lifestyle, fashion involvement, predecision stage, and post-decision stage. According to Stern (1962), the classification of impulsive buying is divided into four types: pure impulse buying, reminder impulse buying, suggestion impulse buying, and planned impulse buying. According to Budiono et al. (2017), there are four main indicators of impulsive buying: spontaneity, pleasure and stimulation, the urge to buy immediately, and indifference to the consequences.

Post-purchase Regret

Post-purchase regret is a form of negative emotion that arises after consumers make a purchase, arising from dissatisfaction with the outcome or decision-making process (Tsiros & Mittal, 2000; Connolly & Zeelenberg, 2002). This feeling of regret occurs when consumers feel that other alternatives might have provided better results, or when the purchasing process is deemed inappropriate (Moakhar et al., 2018; Lee & Cotte, 2009). According to Hung Ku (2005), several factors influence post-purchase regret, including job responsibility, gender, and personality. According to Lee & Cotte (2009), post-purchase regret indicators are divided into two types: outcome regret and process regret.

Content Marketing and Impulsive Buying

According to the consumer behavior model proposed by Kotler and Keller (2016), content marketing plays a role as a marketing stimulus, particularly in the marketing communications received by consumers. Effective communication through content marketing can influence individual perceptions, motivations, and emotions, thus encouraging impulsive buying in response to the stimuli generated by these marketing stimuli. Content marketing, which presents informative, creative, and relevant content, provides an external stimulus that psychologically influences consumers to make impulsive purchases. Research conducted by Indriawan and Santoso (2025) shows that content marketing has a significant positive effect on impulsive buying, with indicators of relevance, accuracy, value, ease of understanding, ease of finding, and consistency. These research results are also supported by Anggara & Widjaja (2025), who stated that the higher the quality of content marketing, the higher the intensity of impulsive buying. Hypothesis 1: Content marketing has a significant effect on impulsive buying.

Fear of Missing Out and Impulsive Buying

According to the consumer behavior model proposed by Kotler & Keller (2016), marketing stimuli are not only physical but also involve psychological and social aspects that influence consumer motivation and perception in purchasing decisions. FoMO is a psychological stimulus that can create urgency and social anxiety, thus driving consumers to engage in impulsive buying as an effort to avoid missing out on opportunities or experiences perceived by others. Previous research supports the influence of FoMO

on impulsive buying, finding that Fear of Missing Out significantly influences impulsive buying of skincare products on online shopping platforms. This finding was further reinforced by Qathrinada and Pandjaitan (2024), who demonstrated that high levels of FoMO among Avoskin consumers in Bandar Lampung increased their tendency to make impulsive purchases. These research findings support the assertion that FoMO can trigger impulsive buying in response to trends and social pressures, and the higher the perceived level of FoMO, the greater the intensity of impulsive buying behavior.

Hypothesis 2: Fear of Missing Out has a significant effect on Impulsive Buying

Content Marketing and Post-Purchase Regret

According to the consumer behavior model proposed by Kotler and Keller (2016), the consumer decision-making process is influenced by various factors, one of which is exposure to marketing information that shapes consumer perceptions and expectations about a product. Content marketing, as part of e-marketing exposure, plays a crucial role in providing relevant and engaging information before consumers make a purchase. However, if the information conveyed through content marketing does not align with the actual experience consumers experience after purchase, this can lead to post-purchase regret, or regret arising from a mismatch between expectations and reality regarding the product. Research by Lubis et al. (2022) shows that e-marketing exposure, including content marketing, can minimize post-purchase regret if conducted transparently and accurately. The study found that honest and informative content marketing practices help consumers form realistic expectations, thereby reducing the risk of post-purchase regret. Conversely, if content marketing creates excessive or unrealistic expectations, this can actually increase the likelihood of post-purchase regret. Therefore, a sound content marketing strategy is crucial for maintaining consumer satisfaction and minimizing post-purchase regret.

Hypothesis 3: Content Marketing has a significant effect on post-purchase regret

Fear of Missing Out and Post-Purchase Regret

According to Kotler and Keller (2016), the consumer decision-making process is heavily influenced by psychological and social factors, including social pressure and exposure to information in the digital environment. One prominent psychological factor is FoMO, the fear of missing out on trends or experiences trending in the social environment, which can shape consumer perceptions and expectations before and after making a purchase. Research by Nuralmasari et al. (2024) shows that FoMO has a positive and significant effect on post-purchase regret among consumers of skincare products on online platforms. This study found that the higher the level of FoMO consumers experience, the greater their likelihood of experiencing post-purchase regret, especially if the purchase decision was made spontaneously without careful consideration due to social pressure or the desire to follow trends. This aligns with the findings of Serdar Ogel (2022), whose research on digital consumer behavior also demonstrated that FoMO directly increases the risk of post-purchase regret.

Hypothesis 4: Fear of Missing Out has a significant effect on post-purchase regret.

Impulsive Buying and Post-Purchase Regret

According to the consumer behavior theory proposed by Kotler and Keller (2016), consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by psychological factors, including emotional impulses. When consumers make impulsive purchases without careful consideration, this aligns with the concept of post-purchase behavior, which states that impulsive buying decisions have the potential to lead to post-purchase regret if the purchase outcome does not meet expectations. Previous research supports the influence of impulsive buying on post-purchase regret. Kumar et al. (2020) found a positive and significant relationship between impulsive buying and post-purchase regret in grocery consumers, where impulsive buying behavior tends to increase the likelihood of consumers experiencing post-purchase regret. Furthermore, Nurohman and Azis (2020) also showed similar results, indicating that impulsive buying significantly influences post-purchase regret in college students. This study revealed that the higher the impulsive buying behavior, the greater the level of regret felt after the purchase. Both findings reinforce the idea that impulsive buying can trigger post-purchase regret in consumers.

Hypothesis 5: Impulsive Buying has a significant effect on Post-Purchase Regret

RESEARCH METHOD

The type of research used is quantitative research. The measurement of the Content Marketing variable refers to the opinion of Milhinhos (2015). The FoMO variable is measured using indicators developed by Joseph Reagle (2015). The Impulsive Buying variable is measured using the opinion of Budiono et al (2017). While the Post-purchase regret variable is measured using the indicator of Lee & Cotte (2009). The sample used was 100 respondents who were buyers and users of Somethinc products and were active members of the Twitter community (X) "Oh My Beauty Bank". The sampling technique used was non-probability sampling with purposive sampling. The data collection method was with Google Form. Data analysis used Descriptive Statistical Analysis and Inferential Analysis using SmartPLS.

RESULT

Respondent Characteristics

Table 1 shows that 91 respondents or 91 percent are women and 9 respondents or 9 percent are men. This shows that most of the respondents are women. Based on gender, the number of respondents in this study is dominated by women. This fact can be understood because Somethinc is a brand that sells beauty products for women. Of the 100 respondents, the age of the respondents is grouped into 4 parts. Based on this grouping, it shows that the age of 21-25 years is the most buyers and users of Somethinc products in the Twitter community (x) "Oh My Beauty Bank", while the age group with the least purchases of this product is the 31-35 year group.

Table 1. Characteristics Respondents (n=100)

Description		percent
Gender	Woman	91
	Man	9
Age	17 - 20	22
	21 - 25	64
	26 - 30	13
	31 - 35	1

Inferential Statistical Analysis

This study used an inferential statistical analysis method with a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach, specifically the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method. The inferential statistical analysis in this study included two stages of model evaluation: the Outer Model (measurement model) evaluation and the Inner Model (structural model) evaluation.

Convergent Validity

Evaluation of convergent validity in testing the reliability of each item can be conducted by examining the standardized loading factor value. This value represents the level of correlation between each measurement indicator and the construct it represents.

Figure 1. Path Diagram with Loading Factor Values

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that the magnitude of the loading factors all have >0.6. This can be interpreted as meaning that overall, each latent variable has been able to explain the variance of each indicator that measures it.

Table 2. Outer Loading Processing Results

	Content Marketing	Fear of Missing Out	Impulsive Buying	Post-purchase regret
CM1	0.859			
CM2	0.898			
CM3	0.902			
CM4	0.899			
CM5	0.926			
CM6	0.923			
FM1		0.908		

FM2	0.904	
FM3	0.903	
FM4	0.915	
PPR1		0.893
PPR2		0.870
PPR3		0.915
PPR4		0.893
IB2		0.929
IB3		0.945
IB4		0.933

Based on Table 2, the results of the analysis indicate that the scores for each construct indicator meet convergent validity and meet the loading factor threshold of >0.7 . Therefore, it can be concluded that the indicators used in this study are sufficient to describe each construct or variable being measured.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity in the reflective model is evaluated using cross-loading. Cross-loading is measured by comparing the correlation between indicators with their primary construct and constructs from other blocks.

Table 3. Cross Loading Processing Results

	Content Marketing	Fear of Missing Out	Impulsive Buying	Post-purchase regret
CM1	0.859	0.260	0.505	0.337
CM2	0.898	0.250	0.429	0.299
CM3	0.902	0.187	0.454	0.345
CM4	0.899	0.216	0.399	0.343
CM5	0.926	0.176	0.448	0.420
CM6	0.923	0.167	0.442	0.370
FM1	0.171	0.908	0.563	0.408
FM2	0.248	0.904	0.537	0.394
FM3	0.231	0.903	0.510	0.413
FM4	0.193	0.915	0.530	0.440
PPR1	0.414	0.578	0.893	0.609
PPR2	0.418	0.530	0.870	0.687
PPR3	0.455	0.538	0.915	0.694
PPR4	0.485	0.463	0.893	0.699
IB1	0.327	0.391	0.690	0.911
IB2	0.313	0.443	0.678	0.929
IB3	0.406	0.442	0.751	0.945
IB4	0.408	0.419	0.680	0.933

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that items CM1, CM2, CM3, CM4, CM5, and CM6 have higher correlation values to their constructs, namely Content Marketing with correlation coefficients of 0.859, 0.898, 0.902, 0.899, 0.926, and 0.923. In items FM1, FM2, FM3, and FM4 have higher correlation values to their constructs, namely FoMO with correlation coefficients of 0.908, 0.904, 0.903, and 0.915. In items PPR1, PPR2, PPR and PPR4 have higher correlation values to their constructs, namely Post-purchase regret with correlation coefficients of 0.893, 0.870, 0.915 and 0.893. In items IB1, IB2, IB3, and IB4 have higher correlation values to their constructs, namely 0.911, 0.929, 0.945, and 0.933. Based on these results, all indicators have a higher correlation coefficient with each construct compared to the correlation coefficient values of indicators in the construct block in other columns, thus it can be concluded that all items have good discriminant validity.

Composite Reliability

Other reliability studies can be measured using composite reliability values obtained from composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. Composite reliability has the same interpretation as Cronbach's alpha. A value of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha is acceptable, and a value of >0.8 is very satisfactory. The composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values in this study can be seen in the following table:

Table 4. Composite Reliability Processing Results

	Cronbach's alpha	rho_a	Composite reliability	AVE
CM	0.954	0.956	0.963	0.813
FM	0.929	0.929	0.949	0.824
IB	0.948	0.950	0.962	0.864
PPR	0.915	0.916	0.940	0.797

Based on Table 4, it shows that the composite reliability of all constructs has a value of more than 0.7, so it can be concluded that all constructs in the model have high reliability and meet the reliable criteria.

Inner Model Evaluation

The next step in the analysis is to evaluate the inner model or structural model. The purpose of this evaluation is to predict the relationship between existing latent variables. Assessment of the inner model in the PLS approach can be seen through the path coefficient, which indicates how strong the relationship between constructs is. Meanwhile, the level of significance of this relationship can be analyzed using the t-test or Critical Ratio (CR) generated by the bootstrapping technique or resampling method. The evaluation of the inner model also includes observing the R-square value of each dependent latent variable, as well as calculating the Q-square. In testing, the R-square value is used to examine the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The results of the R-square re-estimation using smartPLS can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Results of Coefficient Determination

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Impulsive Buying	0.295	0.281
Post-purchase regret	0.685	0.675

Based on Table 5, it shows that the Content Marketing and Fear of Missing Out variables influence the Impulsive Buying variable in the structural model with an adjusted R-Square value of 0.281, which means that the ability of the Content Marketing and FoMo variables to explain the Impulsive Buying variable is 28.1%, while the rest is influenced by other variables outside this study. Content Marketing, FoMo, and Impulsive Buying influence the Post-purchase regret variable in the structural model with an adjusted R-square value of 0.675, which means that the ability of the Content Marketing, FoMo, and Impulsive Buying variables to influence the Post-purchase regret variable is 67.5%, and the rest is influenced by other variables in this study.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is conducted to determine whether there is an influence between the variables in the study. Hypothesis testing can be performed by analyzing the t-statistic and path coefficient values generated through the PLS bootstrapping model, which will produce a t-statistic value. If the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value, the proposed research hypothesis is accepted. If the t-statistic value is less than the t-table value, the proposed research hypothesis is rejected. Bootstrapping will yield a t-statistic value. If the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value, the proposed hypothesis in this study is accepted, and vice versa. The PLS Bootstrapping model in this study can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. PLS Bootstrapping Model

Table 7. Hypothesis Test Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T (O/STDEV)	Statistic P Values	Information
H1	0.303	0.031	0.083	3,656	0.000	Accepted
H2	0.386	0.389	0.123	3,146	0.002	Accepted
H3	0.219	0.225	0.077	2,855	0.004	Accepted
H4	0.296	0.299	0.122	2,436	0.015	Accepted
H5	0.533	0.521	0.149	3,572	0.000	Accepted

Content Marketing has a significant influence on Impulsive Buying, with a t-statistic of $3.656 > 1.96$. The t-statistic is greater than the t-table value, indicating that Content Marketing (X1) has a significant influence on Impulsive Buying (Z). This value indicates a positive relationship between Content Marketing and Impulsive Buying, meaning that the more effective Content Marketing is, the greater the consumer's urge to make impulsive purchases. Therefore, the first hypothesis of this study is accepted.

FoMO has a significant influence on Impulsive Buying, with a t-statistic of $3.146 > 1.96$. This t-statistic is greater than the t-table value, indicating that FoMO (X2) has a significant influence on Impulsive Buying (Z). This value indicates a positive relationship between FoMO and Impulsive Buying, meaning that the stronger the consumer's Fear of Missing Out, the higher their tendency to make impulsive purchases. Thus, the second hypothesis in this study is accepted.

Content Marketing has a significant influence on Post-purchase regret, with a t-statistic of $2.855 > 1.96$. The t-statistic is greater than the t-table value, indicating that Content Marketing (X1) has a significant influence on Post-purchase regret (Y). This value indicates a positive relationship between Content Marketing and Post-purchase regret, meaning that the more effective Content Marketing is, the higher the likelihood of consumers experiencing Post-purchase regret. Therefore, the third hypothesis in this study is accepted.

FoMO has a significant influence on Post-purchase regret, with a statistical value of $2.436 > 1.96$. The statistical value is greater than the t-table value, indicating that FoMO (X2) has a significant influence on Post-purchase regret (Y). This value indicates a positive relationship between FoMO and Post-purchase regret, meaning that the higher the FoMO experienced by consumers, the higher the likelihood of consumers experiencing Post-purchase regret. Therefore, the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted.

Impulsive Buying has a significant influence on the Post-purchase regret variable with a t-statistic value of $3.572 > 1.96$. The t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value, so it can be said that Impulsive Buying (Z) has a significant influence on Post-purchase regret (Y). This value indicates that there is a positive relationship between Impulsive Buying and Post-purchase regret, which means that the higher the tendency of consumers to make Impulsive Buying, the greater the influence on Post-purchase regret. Thus, the fifth hypothesis in the study is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Content Marketing on Impulsive Buying

The results of the hypothesis test indicate a significant influence between Content Marketing and Impulsive Buying among buyers and users of Somethinc products who are members of the "Oh My Beauty Bank" community. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between Content Marketing and Impulsive Buying. This research is supported by the theory of Kotler and Keller (2016), which states that Content Marketing is a form of marketing stimuli, particularly in the marketing communications received by consumers. Effective communication through Content Marketing can influence individual perceptions, motivations, and emotions, thus encouraging impulsive buying in response to these marketing stimuli. This research is supported by research conducted by Indriawan and Santoso (2022), which found that Content Marketing had a significant positive effect on impulsive buying. This is also supported by research conducted by Anggara and Widjaja (2022), which found similar results. The results of this study support the statement of Indriawan and Santoso (2022) that Content Marketing can influence Impulsive Buying with indicators of Relevance, Accuracy, Value, Easy to understand, Easy to find, and Consistency. The results of this study also support the statement by Anggara and Widjaja (2025) where the higher the Content Marketing, the higher the intensity of Impulsive Buying. Therefore, to encourage Impulsive Buying of Something products in the Twitter Community (X) "Oh My Beauty Bank", Content Marketing strategies need to be focused on increasing the relevance and accuracy of information so that consumers feel their needs are met and the information received is factual. In addition, content also needs to be made more engaging to arouse pleasure and emotional interest. Utilizing features such as polls or interactive threads remains important, as long as they are supported by relevant, accurate content and are able to trigger positive emotions in consumers.

The Influence of FoMO on Impulsive Buying

The results of the hypothesis test indicate a significant influence between FoMO and impulsive buying among buyers and users of Somethinc products who are members of the "Oh My Beauty Bank" community. This study aligns with the theory of Kotler and Keller (2016), which states that marketing stimuli are not only physical but also involve psychological and social factors that influence consumer motivation and perception in making purchasing decisions. FoMO, as a psychological stimulus, can create urgency and social anxiety, prompting consumers to engage in impulsive buying as an attempt to miss out on opportunities or experiences experienced by others. This study's findings are supported by research conducted by Nurmalasari et al. (2024), which found FoMO significantly influences impulsive buying of skincare products in online shops. This is also supported by research conducted by Qathrinnada & Pandjaitan (2024), which demonstrated similar results among Avoskin consumers in Bandar Lampung. These results support the statement of Nurmalasari et al. (2024) found that FoMO can trigger impulsive buying as a response to trends and social pressure. This study also supports Qathrinnada & Pandjaitan's (2024) statement that the higher the level of FoMO consumers experience, the greater their tendency to make impulsive purchases. Therefore, to increase Impulsive Buying of Somethinc products through FoMO in the Twitter Community (X) "Oh My Beauty Bank", marketing strategies need to pay attention to the aspect of comparison with other users, especially in situations where consumers feel uncomfortable because they have not tried products that other users have tried. In addition, promotional content also needs to be designed to be more able to arouse pleasure and emotional interest, so that the urge to buy impulsively can increase. This effort can be done by creating content that highlights the positive experiences of other users, while still triggering curiosity and positive emotions in consumers.

The Influence of Content Marketing on Post-Purchase Regret

The results of the hypothesis test indicate a significant influence between the variable Content Marketing (in this case, e-marketing exposure) and post-purchase regret in consumers making online purchases. This finding aligns with the theory of Kotler & Keller (2016), which states that consumer purchasing decisions are strongly influenced by the marketing communications they receive, whether through digital content, images, or promotional videos. Intensive exposure to Content Marketing can shape consumer expectations about the product being offered. However, when the marketing content does not align with the actual product received, this can lead to dissatisfaction and feelings of regret after the purchase, as explained in post-purchase behavior by Kotler & Keller. Research by Lubis et al. (2022) supports this finding by showing that direct e-marketing exposure has a positive and significant influence on regret in online purchases. Lubis et al. highlighted that consumers are often only able to assess products through marketing content in the form of photos or videos, so that if there is a difference between the expectations built by the content and the reality of the product received, consumers tend to experience Post-purchase regret. In addition, this study also emphasized that disproportionate or excessive exposure to Content Marketing can increase the likelihood of consumers feeling disappointed and regretful after purchasing, especially if the information conveyed is not transparent or misleading. Therefore, to minimize Post-purchase regret among buyers of Somethinc products in the Twitter Community (X) "Oh My Beauty Bank", Content Marketing strategies need to emphasize more on presenting information that is relevant to consumer needs and accurate according to the facts. This is important so that consumers do not feel that the product they purchased is less meaningful or does not meet their expectations after purchasing, so that post-purchase regret can be minimized.

The Influence of FoMO on Post-Purchase Regret

The results of the hypothesis test indicate a significant influence between FoMO and post-purchase regret in online skincare consumers. This finding aligns with the theory of Kotler & Keller (2016), which states that consumer purchasing decisions are heavily influenced by psychological factors, including emotional impulses such as FoMO, which encourage individuals to make purchasing decisions to avoid feeling left behind by trends or social experiences. When consumers are driven to make purchases due to FoMO, they are at greater risk of experiencing post-purchase regret, especially if the product purchased does not meet their expectations or needs. This aligns with Kotler & Keller's concept of post-purchase behavior, where emotional distress can trigger post-purchase regret.

This study supports the findings of Nurmalasari et al. (2024), who found that FoMO significantly influences consumption behavior and post-purchase regret in online skincare consumers, both directly and indirectly through impulsive buying. This study confirms that FoMO can increase consumers' tendency to regret past purchases, as decisions are made under emotional stress and a fear of missing out. In addition, Sonmezay's (2023) research also shows that FoMO is triggered by the habit of using social media and exposure to advertisements on these platforms significantly encouraging impulsive buying behavior. Purchases made under the influence of FoMO then increase the possibility of post-purchase regret, even leading to the intention to return the product. This finding confirms that FoMO not only influences spontaneous purchasing decisions, but also has an impact on consumer dissatisfaction and regret after the transaction has taken place. Therefore, to reduce post-purchase regret among Somethinc product buyers in the Twitter Community (X) "Oh My Beauty Bank", it is important for marketing strategies to pay attention to the aspect of comparison with other users, especially when consumers feel uncomfortable because they have not tried products that others have tried. If this FoMO feeling is not managed properly, consumers can be encouraged to buy just because they want to follow the trend,

but ultimately feel that the purchased product is less meaningful or does not meet expectations after the purchase. Thus, managing consumer expectations and experiences is key to minimizing post-purchase regret.

The Effect of Impulsive Buying on Post-Purchase Regret

The results of the hypothesis test indicate a significant effect between the variable Impulsive Buying and the variable Post-Purchase Regret among buyers and users of Somethinc products who are members of the "Oh My Beauty Bank" community. This study's findings align with the theory of Kotler & Keller (2016), which states that consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by psychological factors, including emotional drives. When consumers make impulsive purchases without careful consideration, this aligns with the concept of post-purchase behavior according to Kotler & Keller, where impulsive decisions have the potential to lead to post-purchase regret if the purchase outcome does not meet expectations. This study's findings support the findings of Kumar et al. (2020), who found a positive and significant relationship between impulsive buying and post-purchase regret among grocery consumers. This study indicates that impulsive buying behavior tends to increase the likelihood of consumers experiencing post-purchase regret. Furthermore, research conducted by Nurohman and Azis (2020) also showed similar results, indicating that impulsive buying significantly influenced post-purchase regret in college students. This study revealed that the higher the impulsive buying behavior, the greater the level of regret felt after the purchase. These two findings support the research finding that impulsive buying can trigger post-purchase regret in consumers. Therefore, to minimize post-purchase regret due to impulsive buying among Somethinc product buyers, efforts must be made to ensure that the urge to buy is not solely based on momentary pleasure or emotional attraction upon viewing the product. If purchases are made impulsively without careful consideration, consumers risk feeling the product is less meaningful or does not meet expectations after purchase, leading to regret. Therefore, marketing strategies should also provide space for consumers to rationally consider the product's benefits before deciding to purchase.

Research Limitation

The study has provided an empirical overview of the influence of Content Marketing and FoMO on Post-purchase regret Pr among buyers and users of Somethinc products in the Twitter Community (X) "Oh My Beauty Bank" with Impulsive Buying as a mediating variable. However, this study has several limitations that need to be considered for further research development. This study uses a quantitative approach with an instrument in the form of a Google Form-based questionnaire distributed online. This allows for perception bias because respondents answer based on subjective memories or experiences, not from direct observation of purchasing behavior. In addition, the distribution of questionnaires was carried out non-randomly through purposive sampling, which although appropriate for the target audience, still opens up the possibility of a lack of representation of the wider population.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that Content Marketing and FoMO have a significant influence on Impulsive Buying. The more interesting, relevant, and persuasive the content presented, and the higher the level of FoMO perceived by consumers, the tendency to make impulsive purchases of Somethinc products will increase. Furthermore, both Content Marketing and FoMO are also proven to significantly influence Post-purchase Regret, indicating that overly persuasive marketing communications and the emotional drive of FoMO can increase the potential for post-purchase regret. In addition,

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